

Charge Density Study using Low Electrode Diameter in Epiretinal Prosthesis

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Abstract—Reducing electrode size can be advantageous for stimulating the retina because they produce focal stimulation, i.e. one active electrode excites a single cell thereby greatly increasing resolution. The main limitation is, however, the high charge density of low electrode area that can cause adverse tissue reactions. In this study, we analyze the use of rectangular and linear increase pulse shapes based on charge injection capacity, voltage window and threshold current using a single ganglion cell model with PEDOT-NaPSS arranged electrode array. We found that 100 μ s linear increase pulse shape delivers a better response of charge density and electrode potential than rectangular that would avoid irreversible Faradaic reactions.

Index Terms—charge injection capacity, linear increase pulse, low electrode, rectangular pulse shape, retinal implant, voltage window.

I. INTRODUCTION

RETINAL prosthetic devices have strived to replace the functionality of photoreceptors lost because of degenerative diseases such as retinitis pigmentosa (RP) or age-related macular degeneration (AMD). These diseases are incurable by current treatments. Although the ability to create visual sensations is now well established [1], the quality of vision elicited by retinal implants is facing further challenges for safely electrode implantation.

Decreasing electrode dimensions will allow focal excitation of small groups of cells that lead to high resolution patterns of prosthetic-elicited activity and improve visual reception. This challenge, however, requires higher charge density that can cause breakdown of the electrode as well as adverse tissue reactions [2].

The electrochemical reactions at the electrode-tissue interface, i.e. capacitive double-layer charging, reversible Faradaic and irreversible Faradaic reactions, carry out charge injection into the neural tissue [3,4,5]. The latter reaction can produce electrolysis of water that leads to localized pH changes [6], gas bubble formation that thought to be harmful and physically disturbs the tissue [4, 5] and chemical species formation that damage the tissue or the electrode [3].

Having as a rule of thumb that one should avoid the onset of irreversible Faradaic processes when designing electrical stimulation systems, this would impose to keep the injected charge density at a low level within reversible charge injection processes.

A novel strategy has been proposed [3] that generally suggest keeping the pulse width narrower because it confines the amount of current that can be delivered by a stimulator, especially if it is battery operated, and provides the minimum charge that occurs when pulse width is of tens of μ s.

There is evidence that single linear increase pulse shape at lower pulse durations can deliver lower charge than rectangular, linear decrease and sinusoidal pulse shapes [7].

Furthermore, electrolysis of water occurs as a result when maximum cathodic and anodic potential across the electrodes surpass the “water window” boundary [8]. The water window is a potential range that is defined by the reduction of water, forming hydrogen gas, in the negative direction, and the oxidation of water, forming oxygen, in the positive direction which may cause corrosion.

Once the electrode potential attains either of these two voltage window boundaries, all further injected charge goes into the irreversible Faradaic processes of water oxidation or water reduction [3].

PEDOT is a conductive polymer has been generated considerable attention as a supercapacitor material due to its large electroactive voltage window, high chemical stability among conductive polymers [9], lower impedance and higher charge injection capacity, Q_{INJ} [10]. Q_{INJ} is defined as the amount of charge per unit area that can be delivered through an electrode without causing water electrolysis.

The aim of this study is to investigate the use of rectangular and linear increase pulse shapes based on charge injection capacity, voltage window and threshold current using a single ganglion cell model with PEDOT-NaPSS arranged electrode array. We give some advice on carrying out efficient stimulation by avoiding damage to the tissue and to the electrode.

II. METHODS

A. Ganglion Cell Model

Ganglion cell model has a basic mathematical structure for voltage-gating based on Hodgkin and Huxley like equations [11] and is modelled with an equivalent circuit taken from previously published model of repetitive firing of retinal

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ganglion cells [12]. The parameters and equations that describe the dynamics of the ionic channels were kept as in the original model.

B. Retinal Model

We used the identical COMSOL model of the retina as seen in [13]. The model is shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Retina model at COMSOL simulations. Layer thicknesses not drawn to scale

It consists of seven domains: polyimide carrier of electrodes P_C ; vitreous medium V_M ; retina ganglion cell layer R_{GC} ; photoreceptor layer P_{RC} ; retinal pigment epithelium R_{PE} ; ganglion cell soma S_G and the electrode array E_{ELE} . The ganglion cell soma was placed inside the retina ganglion cell layer exactly below the center of active electrode and was enclosed with the cell membrane.

The material coating the electrode is PEDOT-NaPSS electrodeposited in gold electrodes with a charge density of 40 mC/cm^2 as seen in [10].

The electrode array configuration is shown at the cross section plane in figure 1. This arrangement is analogous to [14,15] however it consists of an active electrode (in red) surrounded by eight guards (in blue) in order to stress the isolation of the active electrode, to confine the stimulus current to a small volume around the ganglion cell and to minimize electrode cross-talk during stimulation.

C. Simulation Procedure – Ganglion Cell Model (Matlab)

In this work we used the identical ganglion cell model as in [12] to calculate in Matlab the extracellular threshold current density of the ganglion cell by applying monophasic rectangular and linear increase pulse shapes to the model at 500 pulses per second, taking into account absolute and refractory period of an action potential.

We followed the strategy as seen in [3] and we chose two pulse duration, Δt , of 50 and 100 μs . Pulse widths lower than 150 μs are analogous in [2] to directly stimulate the ganglion cell and to elicit solely a single spike with precise temporal pattern. The peak current density amplitude was swept with a resolution of $1 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ until it was found the threshold current density that fires a train of action potential.

The result of extracellular peak current amplitude are 330 and 120 $\mu\text{A/cm}^2$ for rectangular pulse shape and 340 and 160 $\mu\text{A/cm}^2$ for linear increase at 50 and 100 μs , respectively.

D. Simulation Procedure – Retinal 3D Model (COMSOL)

The retinal modelling was built in COMSOL and shown in

figure 1. In this work we used the identical retinal model as in [13].

The ganglion cell soma was placed inside the retina ganglion cell layer exactly below the center of active electrode and was enclosed with the cell membrane.

In previous published works [16,17,18,19,20] there have been sufficient evidence that monophasic pulse allows the formation of Faradaic reduction reactions. If oxygen is presence, these reactions may include reduction of oxygen and formation of reactive oxygen species associated in tissue damage.

Although monophasic is the most efficient pulse for stimulation because of the action potential initiation and the potential becomes insufficiently positive (using cathodic pulses) where electrode corrosion may occur, however, it is not used in continuous pulses where tissue damage is to be avoided [3].

We used, however, monophasic rectangular and linear increase shapes with a single anodic pulse for the solely intention to reduce the computational time consumed.

We iterated the retinal model for each E_D , I_{EGD} and Δt until we match the average boundary current density of the cell with the extracellular threshold current amplitude obtained in Matlab by applying current from the active electrode.

We assumed that the irreversible Faradaic reactions, if present, will occur such that the charge density surpass the Q_{INJ} limit or the anodic peak potential at the electrode surpass the voltage window boundary.

The inter electrode ganglion cell distance, I_{EGD} , are 2, 10, 100 μm . The electrode diameter, E_D , are 2, 10 50, 100 μm . The Δt are 50 and 100 μs . We briefly analyzed pulse duration of 150 μs and yielded the highest charge density than 50 and 100 μs .

Out of COMSOL simulations, we also obtained the voltage across the electrodes over time.

E. Charge Density Calculation

The charge density was obtained by integrating the current delivered by the active electrode over time and dividing it by the electrode area. It is worth to mention that all eight surrounding electrodes including the active changed their dimensions accordingly.

Q_{INJ} of gold microelectrode coated with PEDOT-NaPSS follows a linear relationship with charge density used during electropolymerization, Q_D , with a constant $0.075 Q_{INJ}$ per Q_D (until 300 mC/cm^2) for 0.001 and 1 mm^2 electrode size [10].

Q_{INJ} may also be increased by increasing electrochemical surface area [21].

As there is no evidence about Q_{INJ} in PEDOT-NaPSS low electrode area, we used the limit of 0.35 mC/cm^2 for gas-free and erosion-free operation [4] and 1 mC/cm^2 for neural damage [22].

F. Voltage Window Boundary

PEDOT voltage window extends beyond conductive materials, such as MnO_2 , from 1.5 V [23] up to 1.7 V [9].

As there is no evidence about voltage window on PEDOT-

NaPSS low electrode area, we used the limit of 1.7 V.

III. RESULTS

A. Charge Density Results

Figures 2 to 4 show the comparison of threshold charge density, left y-axis, and the threshold current for ganglion cell activation, right y-axis, for monophasic rectangular and linear increase pulse shapes.

Each plot shows the results for a specific I_{EGD} . On top of each plot the forbidden region of gas formation and neural damage are shown with a red dashed-line.

Table I lists the minimum electrode diameter [μm] that can be used with their corresponding limit.

The green boxes indicate the suitability to use the minimum electrode diameter tested of 2 μm .

TABLE I
CHARGE DENSITY LIMITS FOR RECTANGULAR/LINEAR INCREASE PULSE SHAPES

I_{EGD}	0.35 mC/cm ² limit		1 mC/cm ² limit	
	50 μs	100 μs	50 μs	100 μs
2 μm	Yes/Yes	Yes/Yes	Yes/Yes	Yes/Yes
10 μm	Yes/Yes	Yes/Yes	Yes/Yes	Yes/Yes
100 μm	18/9.9	14/9.9	9.7/9.3	9.6/9.3

For a successful implant of retinal device, only the lower safe charge density of 0.35mC/cm² should be employed.

B. Voltage across Electrodes Results

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the comparison of voltage across the electrodes. Each plot shows the results for a specific I_{EGD} .

On top of each plot the voltage window boundary is shown with a red dashed-line.

Table II lists the minimum electrode diameter [μm] that can be used for the corresponding limit.

I_{EGD}	VOLTAGE LIMITS FOR PULSE SHAPES			
	Rectangular		Linear Increase	
	50 μs	100 μs	50 μs	100 μs
2 μm	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
10 μm	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
100 μm	9	4.42	9.2	6.3

The green boxes indicate the suitability to use the minimum electrode diameter tested of 2 μm .

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Threshold Current

Threshold currents, figures 2 to 4, were found to increase with time after surgery, most likely due to the lifting off of the electrode array from the retinal surface [24].

Threshold variations with respect to I_{EGD} are consistent with previous experimental work of epiretinal device implanted in rabbits [25].

Because linear increase shape injects less charge than rectangular for a given pulse duration, the former necessitates a higher amplitude to reach threshold.

B. Charge Density

It is evident that the charge density, figures 2 to 4, decreases using linear increase pulse shape.

Fig. 2. Threshold charge density and threshold current for 2 μm inter electrode-ganglion cell distance.

Using 50 μs pulse duration, charge density is reduced up to $40\pm 2.4\%$ in average; for 100 μs , it is decreased $30\pm 1.3\%$. This means a promising technique to avoid irreversible Faradaic reactions.

The rectangular pulse shape has its own attributes meaning that using E_D of 2 μm , 50 or 100 μs pulse duration, and I_{EGD} lower than 10 μm is safe within the limits. This technique works with linear increase pulse shape as well. Doing so, it provides a method to send a more natural signal to the brain and to generate meaningful percepts.

Figure 4 show the constraint of charge density at both limits mainly when I_{EGD} is greater than 10 μm .

Fig. 3. Threshold charge density and threshold current for 10 μm inter electrode-ganglion cell distance.

For achieving a better response in continuous pulses, charge-imbalanced biphasic waveform provides a method to reduce the irreversible charge density as reactions occurring in one phase (cathodic or anodic) are reverse in the following [3].

Furthermore, it was demonstrated that this waveform allows greater cathodic charge densities than monophasic prior to the onset of tissue damage [26].

C. Voltage across Electrodes

It is also evident that using 100 μs pulse duration, more than one third but less than half of electrode voltage, fig. 5 and 6, is reduced than 50 μs for both pulse shapes. This technique would avoid irreversible Faradaic reactions.

Fig. 4. Threshold charge density and threshold current for 100 μm inter electrode-ganglion cell distance.

Considering figure 5 and 6, we learn that it is safe to work with E_D of 2 μm , low pulse durations lower than 150 μs , I_{EGD} lower than 10 μm with either rectangular or linear increase pulse shapes.

Fig. 5. Voltage results for 2 μm inter electrode-ganglion cell distance for rectangular and linear increase pulse shapes.

Figure 6 show that the constraint of voltage window limit originates mainly when I_{EGD} is greater than 10 μm .

Fig. 6. Voltage results for 10 and 100 μm inter electrode-ganglion cell distance for rectangular and linear increase pulse shapes.

It should be noted that in fact irreversible processes might occur at potentials within the voltage window, such as irreversible oxygen reduction, as opposed to the opinion in many studies that states reversible charge storage capacity, or Q_{INJ} , can be applied without the electrode potential exceeds the voltage window during pulsing [3]. Therefore, Q_{INJ} and voltage window limits need to be analyzed separately.

For attaining a better response in successive pulses, the charge-imbalanced waveform has advantages in avoiding corrosion by decreasing the maximum positive potential since the anodic phase is no longer constrained to be equal to the cathodic phase as charge-balanced pulse, thus the electrode potential reaches less positive values [3,26].

V. CONCLUSIONS

We found that 100 μs linear increase pulse shape delivers a better response of charge density and electrode potential than rectangular that would avoid irreversible Faradaic reactions.

Furthermore, for a given I_{EGD} with charge density limit of 0.35mC/cm² and voltage window limit of 1.7V, our model suggests:

i) $0 < I_{\text{EGD}} < 10 \mu\text{m}$: a) reduce electrode diameter to 2 μm ; b) work with either 50 or 100 μs low pulse duration; c) use either rectangular or linear increase pulse shapes.

ii) $10 < I_{\text{EGD}} < 100 \mu\text{m}$ (for rectangular pulse): a) reduce electrode diameter to 14 μm only with 100 μs pulse duration. For 50 μs , electrode diameter should be 18 μm .

iii) $10 < I_{\text{EGD}} < 100 \mu\text{m}$ (for linear increase pulse): a) reduce electrode diameter to $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ with either 50 or 100 μs pulse duration.

If pulse trains are needed, the charge-imbalanced waveform has added advantages in avoiding corrosion and reducing irreversible charge densities that leads to either electrode or tissue damage [3,26].

Additional experimental testing of small electrodes is still required to verify our results. Moreover, further simulations of heat dissipation should be performed to verify the use of 1000+ electrode array for epi- or subretinal implants.

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